
Determinants of Stock Investment Decisions of Investor in Environmental Wetlands

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to examine the determinants of investment decisions of stock investors in wetland environments. Investment is an activity of investing funds or capital in other parties, either directly or indirectly with the hope that the owner of the capital will get a number of benefits from the results of investing the funds or capital. There are several factors that influence investment decisions including financial literacy, Risk Perception, Financial Experience and Herding.

This study uses a quantitative research approach. The population in this study are the investors in the Wetland Environment, with a sample of 122 investors who fit the predetermined criteria. The sample sampling technique in this study used non-probability sampling. The data that used in the study are primary data, with the data collection method in the form of a questionnaire distributed using google form. The data analysis technique uses multiple regression analysis by first conducting a validity test, reliability test, and classical assumption test.

The results found that Financial Literacy, Financial Experience and Herding behaviour have a positive effect on Investment Decisions, while Risk Perception has no effect on investment decisions.

KEYWORDS: Financial Behaviour, Financial Literacy, Financial Experience, Risk Perception, Herding behaviour and Investment Decision.

INTRODUCTION

Economic conditions in the world are experiencing increasingly rapid development and progress along with globalisation. Economic globalisation has had a major impact on the business world and the economy as a whole. Countries around the world can access the global market to buy or sell goods and services, as well as offer employment for their people. This opens up opportunities to create more jobs, increase productivity, and increase investment that will drive economic growth in a country. One form of investment is investing in the Stock Exchange or Capital Market.

Based on KSEI data as of 3 November 2022, the number of capital market investors in Indonesia referring to the Single Investor Identification (SID) has reached 10,000,628, an increase of 33.53 percent compared to 2021 which was only 7,489,337 SID. Compared to the total population of Indonesia according to the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) report which reached 275.77 million people in 2022, the number of investors in Indonesia is still around 3.63 per cent of the total population in Indonesia. Based on the type of investment in November 2022, 4,323,643 SID or 43.23 per cent of the total SID invested in the stock market and other securities, an increase of 25.27 per cent or 3,451,513 SID in 2021. The positive development of the capital market will certainly increase domestic capital sources. If domestic capital sources increase, it is expected that funds will be available to carry out economic development so that the economy can develop in a positive direction.

South Kalimantan Province ranks 16th in the number of investors out of 34 provinces in Indonesia, based on data from the Financial Services Authority as of December 2022. The number of investors in South Kalimantan is 136,681 SID and of these, 41,852 or 30.62 per cent of the investors are domiciled in Banjarmasin City, followed by Banjar Regency and Banjarbaru City with 14,716 SID and 14,675 SID. Investment activities carried out are closely related to investment decisions made by investors. Investment decisions are policies taken on two or more investment alternatives with the expectation of future profits (Budiarto & Susanti, 2017). Every investor in making an investment decision will be different from other investors.

There are two approaches that study investment decisions made by investors. The first approach is known as the traditional approach or standard finance. Traditional finance theory or referred to as standard finance is represented by the efficient-market hypothesis developed by Fama (1970), which explains that in an efficient market the price of a security formed is a mirror of all available and relevant information about the security. In other words, the price formed is fair value. This means that investors will not earn abnormal returns continuously because other investors will immediately know the actions taken by an investor. so the only

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way to get high returns is by buying riskier investment assets. In addition, the theory of traditional finance itself is often associated with modern portfolio theory. Modern portfolio theory has been pioneered by Markowitz (1952) which explains the importance of diversification to reduce the risk of an investment, with the assumption that investors will behave rationally at all times, predictably and not deviate from generally accepted habits. Thus, investors will only make high-risk investments if they can expect greater returns. However, traditional financial theory does not contribute to explaining the movement of stock prices or other securities. There are often phenomena in the capital market/financial markets that contradict standard financial theory which are often referred to as capital market anomalies such as the January Effect, Day of the week effects, returns over trading and non-trading periods, Stock return volatility and the internet phenomenon.

Based on this, financial researchers began to relate existing phenomena to the second approach, namely the behavioural aspect (behavioural finance). According to Ricciardi and Simon (2000) Behavioural finance tries to explain and improve understanding of the patterns of investor reasoning including emotional aspects and the degree of these aspects in influencing the decision-making process. Olsen (1998) explains that Behavioral Finance does not try to define "rational" behaviour or call decision making as biased or wrong. It seeks to understand and predict the implications of systematic financial markets from a psychological point of view. So it can be concluded that behavioural finance is a science that studies how humans take action on the decision-making process in investing in response to the information they get. From the research conducted, it can be concluded that investors do not always behave rationally and do not deviate and can be modelled quantitatively. Sengupta, Prosad, & Kapoor (2015) suggest that behavioural finance emerged as a branch of social psychology that captures the human side of decision making. According to Alquraan, Alqisie, & Shofa (2016) behavioural finance seeks to discover how investors' emotions and psychology influence investment decisions. Wulandari & Iramani (2014) revealed that investor behaviour that can change at any time is the influence of psychological factors. There are elements of subjectivity, emotions, and other psychological factors that are even more dominant in influencing and even forcing an investor to choose what type of investment they will choose. This study aims to determine the factors that influence individual investor decisions in the Wetland Environment using a behavioural finance approach. There are several factors that influence a person's investment decision including financial literacy, Risk Perception, Financial Experience and Herding behaviour.

According to OECD (2011) Financial Literacy is a concept that combines the behaviour, knowledge, attitudes, and skills, as well as the awareness needed by investors and the public in making good financial decisions for individuals and companies. According to the Financial Services Authority Financial literacy is knowledge, skills, and beliefs that influence attitudes and behaviour to improve the quality of decision making and financial management to achieve public financial welfare. Abdeldayem (2016) Financial literacy is the ability of individuals to utilise skills and knowledge in assessing and managing financial resources efficiently in the long term, with the aim of having good financial health. An individual should have financial skills and knowledge to improve their ability to make rational investment decisions. If investors have good financial literacy, they tend to choose investments with high risk and high returns. This is because by having high financial literacy a person will be more informed and can minimise the risks that will be faced. Braunstein and Welch (2002) state that individuals who have good financial literacy can generally decide and buy investments that have a high level of profit. Several studies on the effect of financial literacy on investment decisions conducted by Dohmen, Falk, Huffman & Minggu (2010), Sabri (2016), Hilgert et al., (2003), Awais et al (2016), Saputro and Lestari (2019) found that financial literacy has a positive influence on investment decisions in the capital market.

The second factor that influences investment decisions is risk perception. Cox and Rich (1964) define risk perception as a person's view of the consequences of risk and uncertainty of profit or loss from a transaction. Ramashar et al. (2022) state that risk perception arises because of the uncertainty faced by individuals when making investment decisions. Someone who has a high risk perception will think about the effect of the investment they will get. Ahmad & Shah (2022) provide a definition of risk perception is how investors perceive the risk of financial assets, based on investor attention and experience. Risk perception is the way individuals understand the level of risk of uncertainty and possible losses associated with investment decisions. Each investor will make investment decisions differently due to the investor's risk perception which creates uncertainty in investment decisions. It can be concluded that risk perception means a person's view of a risk (uncertainty) based on the information received, personal experience and beliefs held. Risk perception affects investor readiness when facing investment risks in the future. Individuals who have a high risk perception will be careful in choosing products to invest in. On the other hand, people who have low risk perception tend to be more courageous in deciding what investment products to buy. An investor when faced with a decision-making situation will certainly consider the risks and impacts first. Based on research from Baghani & Sedaghat (2016), Kharta & Kumar (2014), Ramashar et al., (2022), Ahmad & Shah (2022), Herliana, Ratnawati, and Djumahir (2023) found that risk perception has a positive influence on investment decision making.

The third factor that influences investment decisions is financial experience. Financial experience is learning about financial management, so that an individual who has good financial experience than other individuals will be able to manage their finances more wisely (Susdiani, 2017). Lusardi and Tufano (2015) explain that financial experience is an event experienced by individuals in many financial transactions through careful consideration. Financial experience in question is an event related to financial transactions that have been experienced by individuals such as investment planning, pension funds, insurance, and credit. Based on

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this experience, individuals will consider and plan for future financial management. Individuals who have high financial experience will have many considerations that make it easier for them to manage their finances to make investment decisions faster with better and optimal decision results, namely investment decisions that provide a high level of return with low risk. The results of research conducted by Arifin and Widjaya (2021), Chen, Kim, Nofsinger, & Rui (2007), Pertiwi, Wardani and Septentia (2020), Mandagie et al., (2020) which found that financial experience has a significant positive effect on investment decisions.

The fourth factor influencing investment decisions is Herding Behaviour. According to Luong & Ha (2011), Herding behaviour is identified as the behavioural tendency of investors to follow the actions of others. Lao and Singh (2011) state that herding behaviour is one of the financial behavioural factors that explains that investors follow other investors when making investment decisions. This behaviour of following other investors is carried out because of the indecision of making stock investment decisions. Therefore, investors decide to follow other investments, hoping to minimise risk. Hwang and Salmon (2004) say herding behaviour is a behaviour that follows the decisions of other investors or movements in the financial markets rather than following their own beliefs and information. This means that if changes occur from other investors, they will make changes in their investment decisions. According to Duy Bui, Chi Le, Ngoc Quang, & Wong (2021) Herding behaviour affects investment decisions. In herding behaviour, investors believe that following the ability of other investors will be an option that can be considered. The results of research (Luong and Ha, 2011), Hwang and Salmon (2004), Duy Bui, Chi Le, Ngoc Quang, & Wong (2021), Madaan & Singh (2019), and Lin (2011) found that Herding behaviour has a positive influence on investment decisions.

This study attempts to examine the influence of various psychological factors in investment decision making. The psychological factors to be examined are Financial Literacy, Risk Perception, Financial Experience and Herding behaviour on investment decision making.

RESEARCH METHODS

This was a cross-sectional study and quantitative methods were used for data analysis. The questionnaire was distributed online through Google Form and was distributed to potential respondents through social media. The actual sample size for the study was 122 respondents consisting of 65 men and 57 women. The variables in this study consist of dependent variables, namely investment decisions and independent variables consisting of Financial literacy, risk perception, financial experience and herding behaviour. Investment decisions and financial literacy use 6 indicators, while risk perception, financial experience and herding behaviour use 4 indicators. Measurement of these variables uses a Likert scale from 1 to 5 which has an interval from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The data collected in this study were tested and analysed with validity and reliability tests, classical assumption tests, multiple linear regression tests, F statistical tests, t statistical tests, and the coefficient of determination.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Characteristics

The sample used in this study totalled one hundred and twenty-two active investors in South Kalimantan. Respondent characteristics are used to determine the diversity of respondents based on gender, age, education, occupation, monthly income, and length of time as an investor. This is expected to provide a fairly clear picture of the condition of the respondents and their relationship to the problems and objectives of the study. The following characteristics of the respondents are presented in table 1.

Validity and Reliability Test

Every research conducted using a questionnaire or questionnaire method needs to be tested for validity. The validity test is useful for knowing the validity or suitability of the questionnaire used by researchers to obtain data from respondents or research samples. According to Sugiyono (2017) the validity test is carried out to measure whether the data that has been obtained for use in research is valid data or not, using the measuring instrument used (questionnaire). The validity test in this study uses person correlation with a Degree of freedom of $N-2$ ($122-2$) or 120 samples and a two-way significance level of 0.05, then r table is found to be 0.2104. If r count is greater than r table, the statement item is valid, or it can also be seen from the level of significance. If the significance is less than 0.05, the statement item for that variable is valid. Table 2 shows the validity test results for each statement item that represents the research variable.

Based on table 8. it is known that all statement items in this study, both dependent and independent variables, the calculated r value is greater than the r table value. This means that all statement items in this study are valid or represent the variables used in this study.

Reliability test is a test of instrument measurement which, when used several times to measure the same object, will produce the same data. In this study, the reliability test used Cronbach Alpha. A construct or variable is said to be reliable if it provides a Croanbach Alpha value > 0.60 , it can be said that the instrument used is reliable (Suharsimi, 2006). The testing process was carried out before the actual research was carried out. The results of reliability testing for each variable are summarised in table 3.

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Based on table 3. it is known that the Cronbach Alpha value for each research variable, namely financial literacy, risk perception, financial experience, herding behaviour and investment decisions is greater (>) than 0.60, which means that all concepts measuring each variable from the questionnaire are reliable so that henceforth the items on each variable concept are suitable for use as measuring instruments.

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents

DESCRIPTION	AMOUNT	PERCENTAGE
GENDER		
BOYS	65	53,28%
WOMEN	57	46,72%
AMOUNT	122	100%
AGE		
< 25 years	12	9,84%
25 Years - 35 Years	67	54,92%
36 Years - 45 Years	38	31,15%
> 45 Years	5	4,10%
AMOUNT	122	100,00%
EDUCATION		
HIGH SCHOOL	8	6,56%
D3	6	4,92%
S1	87	71,31%
S2	17	13,93%
S3	4	3,28%
AMOUNT	122	100%
JOB		
STUDENTS	12	9,84%
PRIVATE SECTOR EMPLOYEES	52	42,62%
PNS/TNI/POLRI	20	16,39%
ENTREPRENEUR	30	24,59%
IRT	4	3,28%
OTHER OTHER	4	3,28%
AMOUNT	122	100%
MONTHLY INCOME		
< 5.000.000	32	26,23%
5.000.000 - 10.000.000	28	22,95%
10.000.001 - 15.000.000	21	17,21%
15.000.001 - 20.000.000	31	25,41%
>20.000.000	10	8,20%
AMOUNT	122	100%
LONG TIME INVESTOR		
Less than 2 Years	31	25,41%
2 Years - 5 Years	78	63,93%
More than 5 Years	13	10,66%
AMOUNT	122	100%

Source: Results of questionnaire data processed (2023)

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Table 2. Validity Test Results

Variables	Indicators	r table	r Count	Sig	Ket
FINANCIAL LITERACY (X1)	X1.1	0,2104	0,708	0,000	Valid
	X1.2	0,2104	0,666	0,000	Valid
	X1.3	0,2104	0,529	0,000	Valid
	X1.4	0,2104	0,651	0,000	Valid
	X1.5	0,2104	0,675	0,000	Valid
	X1.6	0,2104	0,55	0,000	Valid
RISK PERCEPTION (X2)	X2.1	0,2104	0,649	0,000	Valid
	X2.2	0,2104	0,742	0,000	Valid
	X2.3	0,2104	0,681	0,000	Valid
	X2.4	0,2104	0,712	0,000	Valid
FINANCIAL EXPERIENCE (X3)	X3.1	0,2104	0,73	0,000	Valid
	X3.2	0,2104	0,837	0,000	Valid
	X3.3	0,2104	0,795	0,000	Valid
	X3.4	0,2104	0,652	0,000	Valid
HERDING BEHAVIOUR (X4)	X4.1	0,2104	0,795	0,000	Valid
	X4.2	0,2104	0,851	0,000	Valid
	X4.3	0,2104	0,889	0,000	Valid
	X4.4	0,2104	0,82	0,000	Valid
INVESTMENT DECISION (Y)	Y1.1	0,2104	0,679	0,000	Valid
	Y1.2	0,2104	0,781	0,000	Valid
	Y1.3	0,2104	0,6	0,000	Valid
	Y1.4	0,2104	0,515	0,000	Valid
	Y1.5	0,2104	0,58	0,000	Valid
	Y1.6	0,2104	0,691	0,000	Valid

Source: SPSS 23 results processed data (2023)

Table 3. Reliability Test Results

VARIABLES	CRONBACH ALPHA	CONCLUSIONS
FINANCIAL LITERACY (X1)	0,715	RELIABLE
RISK PERCEPTION (X2)	0,691	RELIABLE
FINANCIAL EXPERIENCE (X3)	0,642	RELIABLE
HERDING BEHAVIOUR (X4)	0,748	RELIABLE
INVESTMENT DECISION (Y1)	0,859	RELIABLE

Source: SPSS 23 results processed data (2023)

Classical Assumption Test Normality Test

Table 4 shows the results of the normality test using the Kolmogorov Smirnov test. Based on table 4, it can be concluded that the value of Asymp. Sig. (2- tailed) of $0.115 > \alpha = 0.05$, meaning that it is in accordance with decision making using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test which concludes that the data has a normal distribution and has fulfilled the normality requirements in the regression model.

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Table 4. Normality Test Results

		Standardised Residual
N		122
Normal Parameters a,b	Mean	0
	Std Deviation	2,0031
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0,108
	Positive	0,108
	Negative	-0,107
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1,196
Asymp Sig (2-tailed)		0,115
Test Distribution is normal		
Calculated from data		

Source: SPSS results processed data, 2023

Multicollinearity Test

Table 5 shows the results of Multicollinearity testing. Based on table 5, it is known that the Tolerance value for each variable has a result > 0.1 and the VIF value for each variable is < 10. So it can be concluded that the variables of Financial Literacy, Risk Perception, financial experience, and Herding Behaviour do not occur multicollinearity between variables in the regression equation.

Table 5. Multicollinearity Test Results

Collinearity Statistics Variables	Tolerance	VIF
	FINANCIAL LITERACY	0,627
RISK PERCEPTION	0,644	1,552
FINANCIAL EXPERIENCE	0,659	1,517
HERDING BEHAVIOUR	0,845	1,184

Source: SPSS results processed data, 2023

Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity testing in this study uses Scatterplots by making a plot or scatter graph between "Standardised Predicted Value (ZPRED)" and "Studentised Residual (SRESID)". Figure 1. shows the results of the heteroscedasticity test using scatterplots. Based on Figure 1. it can be seen that there is no clear pattern, such as points spreading above and below the number 0 on the Y axis, which means that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity.

Figure 1

Heteroscedasticity Test Scatterplots

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Multiple linear regression analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis aims to determine the dependence between one or two independent variables and the dependent variable, or also to estimate the effect between one independent variable and one dependent variable. The regression analysis test used the Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS) version 25.0 for Windows with $\alpha = 5\%$ (0.05). Table 6 shows the results of multiple Linear regression Analysis.

Table 6. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results

Variables	Unstandardised Coefficients		t Count	sig
	B	Std Error		
(Constant)	7,656	2,076	3,687	0,000
FINANCIAL LITERACY	0,341	0,087	3,903	0,000
RISK PERCEPTION	0,025	0,101	0,252	0,802
FINANCIAL EXPERIENCE	0,347	0,111	3,13	0,002
HERDING BEHAVIOUR	0,186	0,067	2,769	0,007
F Count			18,382	0,000
R Square			0,386	
Adjusted R Square			0,365	

Source: SPSS results processed data, 2023

Based on table 12, the regression model analysis obtained is as follows:

$$KI = 7.656 + 0.341X1 + 0.025X2 + 0.347X3 + 0.186X4$$

The calculated F value is used to test the goodness of fit of the model. The results in the table show the calculated F value of 18.38, while the significant value is $0.000 < 0.05$. So it can be concluded that the regression model is declared feasible (fit). This means that together the variables of Financial Literacy, Risk Perception, Financial Experience, and Herding Behaviour affect Investment Decisions.

The coefficient of determination is carried out to measure how the independent variable affects the overall dependent variable and its effect. This test is seen from the Adjusted R Square value. Based on table 6, the Adjusted R Square value is 0.365. This shows that Financial Literacy, Risk Perception, Financial Experience, and Herding Behaviour are able to simultaneously explain investment decisions by 36.5% after adjusting for the sample and independent variables while the remaining 64.5% is influenced by other variables outside the model.

Based on table 6, the t test results for the Financial Literacy variable show the amount of the t table of the Financial Literacy variable of 3.903 with a significant value of 0.000, which is smaller than the significant level of 0.05. So it can be concluded that H1 is accepted, which means that the Financial Literacy variable has a significant positive effect on Investment Decisions, the Risk Perception variable shows the amount of the t table of the Risk Perception variable of 0.252 with a significant value of 0.802 greater than the significant level of 0.05. So it can be concluded that H2 is rejected, which means that the Risk Perception variable has no effect on Investment Decisions. the Financial Experience variable shows the t table of the Financial Experience variable of 3.13 with a significant value of 0.002, which is smaller than the significant level of 0.05. So it can be concluded that H3 is accepted, which means that the Financial Experience variable has a significant positive effect on Investment Decisions and the Herding Behaviour variable of 2.769 with a significant value of 0.007, which is smaller than the significant level of 0.05. So it can be concluded that H4 is accepted, which means that the Herding Behaviour variable has a significant positive effect on Investment Decisions.

DISCUSSION

This study aims to determine the effect of financial behaviour on investment decisions in investors in the Wetland environment. As is known that Behaviour finance is a science that studies how a person thinks and behaves in making a decision whether as an individual investor or an institutional investor. Many factors, especially from psychology or sociology, can influence a person's actions or behaviour in making a decision. Some psychological and social factors that can influence investment decisions include Financial Literacy, Risk Perception, Financial Experience and Herding Behaviour. The results of this study indicate that Financial Literacy, Financial Experience and Herding Behaviour have a significant positive relationship to Investment Decisions while Risk Perception has no effect on Investment Decisions.

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Financial Literacy is knowledge of financial concepts and the ability to make informed decisions about financial planning and financial management. The results of this study indicate that Financial Literacy has a positive influence on Investment Decisions, this means that the better a person's knowledge and ability to manage their finances, the more effective investment decisions will be. In addition, the ability to determine the type of investment will affect the benefits received by investors in the future. Financial Literacy plays an important role for individuals in making investment decisions. Individuals with a good level of Financial Literacy tend to have better control in determining the right investment and managing their assets because they have more financial information so that investment goals can be achieved and provide good returns as well. The results of this study are in accordance with research conducted by Dohmen, Falk, Huffman & Minggu (2010), Sabri (2016), Hilgert et al., (2003), Awais et al (2016), Saputro and Lestari (2019) who in their research concluded that Financial Literacy has a positive effect on investment decisions.

Risk perception shows how an investor perceives a certain risk so as to make investment decisions that can maximise investor utilisation (Tandelilin, 2017). Perception has an impact on an individual's readiness to take risks. Such readiness depends on uncertain outcomes caused by improper knowledge in the scale of potential losses or gains. So that risk perception plays an important role in human behaviour in making decisions under conditions of uncertainty. The results of this study indicate that risk perception has no effect on investment decisions. Based on the research data, it is known that 64.86 per cent of respondents are less than 35 years old. Younger investors tend not to pay too much attention to risk in investing. In addition, they feel they have the ability and knowledge so that investors have a positive stance that the investment made will definitely be successful or there will be no unexpected risks so they don't think too much about risk when making investment decisions. The results of this study are not in accordance with prospect theory which states that a person makes decisions under certain risk conditions or chooses between two risk options under conditions of uncertainty (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979). It can be interpreted that risk perception behaviour does not affect their view of investment risk will be higher so that it makes them more careful in determining investment decisions. The results of this study are in accordance with the research of Afrida and Sari (2022), and Ahzar, Qurniawati and Nurohman (2023) who found that risk perception has no effect on investment decisions.

Financial Experience is an individual experience that occurs in managing and managing their finances as future considerations and planning in order to meet future needs. The results of this study show that financial experience has a positive influence on investment decisions, this means that the better the individual's financial experience, the better in determining investment decisions. Financial experiences that occur to investors in the wetland environment, be it profitable or unprofitable experiences, will influence investment decision making. From this experience they will learn to understand how the experiences received previously to be used as learning if there are problems in making investment decisions. This financial experience can occur to an individual through transactions that have been made and making an investment decision. This can be used by someone as a consideration in making investment decisions. These considerations are seen from the risks and returns that have a big role in making investment decisions. so that an individual must be more careful in calculating the risks and returns on investment products to be taken. The results of this study are in accordance with the results of research by Arifin and Widjaya (2021), Chen, Kim, Nofsinger, & Rui (2007), Pertiwi, Wardani and Septentia (2020), Mandagie et al., (2020) who found that financial experience has a significant positive effect on investment decisions.

Based on the results of data analysis in this study, herding behaviour has a significant positive effect on investment decisions. Herding behaviour occurs because of something that can cause investors to follow other investors in making investment decisions. Investment decision making by investors in the Wetland Environment is influenced by the decision to sell and buy shares, the volume of trading and the holding period of shares made by other investors. This proves that investors in the Wetland Environment tend to follow the actions of other investors and cause herding behaviour in their investment decision making. The results of this study support behavioural finance theory which states that there are implications of psychological factors that influence investor behaviour. Thus, it can be interpreted that herding behaviour makes investors take irrational actions. Where, they make investment decisions not based on available information, but prefer to follow other investors' decisions and ignore their ability to analyse financial information. The results of this study are reinforced by research conducted by (Luong and Ha, 2011), Hwang and Salmon (2004), Duy Bui, Chi Le, Ngoc Quang, & Wong (2021), Madaan & Singh (2019), and Lin (2011) found that Herding behaviour has a positive influence on investment decisions.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on data analysis and discussion, the conclusion of this study is that financial literacy, financial experience and herding behaviour have a positive and significant influence on stock investment decisions on stock investors in wetland environments. While risk perception has no effect on investment decisions in the wetland environment. Thus, the higher the financial literacy, financial experience and herding behaviour, the higher the level of investor stock investment decisions in the wetland environment.

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